

Peer Review to Improve a Culture of Safety: A Quality Improvement Project

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Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice project is to improve the reporting of medical incidents (MI) by promoting a culture of safety through the development, implementation, and evaluation of an incidence-based peer review (IBPR) process in an acute care urban facility

Medical Incidents

Background

- 98,000 patients die each year from medical incidents (MI)
- 1 in 3 healthcare workers are involved in an MI during their career
- A culture of safety can improve MI reporting
- RNs can identify structure and process changes to mitigate MI

Framework

Model for Improvement

What are we trying to accomplish?
How will we know that a change is an improvement?
What change can we make that will result in improvement?

Associates in Process Improvement (n.d.).

Methods

Design

- Quality improvement project

Setting

- Three adult medical-surgical units acute-care urban facility

Measures

- Outcome measures- MI count, adapted AHRQ- Hospital Surveys of Safety Cultures survey™ (AHRQ-SOPS™)
- Process measures- System causes count, IBPR nurse evaluation
- Balancing measure- IBPR effect on nurse call light response time in minutes

Procedures

- Eight IBPR sessions conducted by staff nurses. Medical incidents reviewed; system causes identified

Analysis

- AHRQ-SOPS™ top box scores (+ worded: agree/always agree; - worded: disagree/always disagree)
- C-chart evaluated for variation in MI pre- post-implementation
- Run charts utilized for system causes found
- Xbar R chart used to assess for variation in call light response time

Results: Adapted AHRQ-SOPS™

Key Findings

- MI reporting did not improve
- IBPR generally improved culture of safety
- An average of 1.3 system causes were found each week in IBPR meetings
- IBPR evaluation by participants had a top box score average of 94%
- Call light response time showed no change

Limitations

- Limited implementation time to allow for change to culture
- Response bias due to Hawthorne effect and use of the Likert scale
- Fears of punitive actions by management

Unanticipated Findings

- Difficulty scheduling pre-meetings and IBPR with nursing staff
- Forced to overlap weekly IBPR meetings with pre-meeting for following week
- Post-implementation MI reporting decreased from baseline
- Post-survey sample size 33 higher than pre-survey with 67 paired samples

Recommendations

- Spread IBPR throughout facility
- IBPR on a monthly schedule
- Line-staff driven committee
- Involve nursing leadership